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NERSC Technical Report no. 186

under contract with

European Space Agency (ESA)

no. 13662/99/I-DC

DECIDE FOR NEAR-REAL-TIME USE OF OCEAN COLOUR DATA IN MANAGEMENT OF HARMFUL ALGAE BLOOMS

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SPECIFICATION, DEFINITION AND DESIGN DOCUMENT

in co-operation with

**Centre for Coastal and Marine Sciences-
Plymouth Marine Laboratory
Plymouth, UK**

**Institute of Marine Research
Bergen, Norway**

EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY CONTRACT REPORT

**The work describes in this report was done
under ESA contract. Responsibility for the
contents resides in the author or organisation
that prepared it.**

**Bergen, September 2000
(version 1.4)**

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REPORT

TITLE DeciDe for near real-time use of ocean colour data in management of harmful algae blooms. Specification, Definition and Design Document	REPORT No. Technical Report no. 186 (Final version 1.4)
CLIENT European Space Agency (ESA)	CONTRACT No. 13662/99/I-DC
CONTACT PERSONS P. Regner, ESA/ESRIN L. Fusco, ESA/ESRIN	AVAILABILITY OPEN
AUTHORS Lasse H. Pettersson ¹ , Dominique D. Durand ¹ , Einar Svendsen ³ , Thomas Noji ³ , Henrik Søliland ³ , Steve Groom ² , Samantha Lavender ²	DATE September 22, 2000
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REMARK This report is the project deliverable focusing on the definition, design and specifications of a service for applications of EO data in the existing service for HAB monitoring in Norwegian waters.	
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ESA STUDY CONTRACT REPORT			
ESA CONTRACT NUMBER: 13662/99/I-DC	SUBJECT DeciDe for near-real-time use of ocean colour data in management of harmful algae blooms.		CONTRACTOR Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center
ESA CR()No	STAR CODE:	NO. OF VOLUMES: 1 THIS VOLUME: 1	CONTRACTOR'S REFERENCE: <i>Technical Report no. 186</i>
<p>ABSTRACT:</p> <p>The importance of the aquaculture industry is significant for the Norwegian economy and the employment in coastal parts of Norway. The development of the industry over the last decades, placed Norway as the world largest export nation for aquaculture fish species, exporting in 1998 around 390,000 tonnes of farmed salmon and trout.</p> <p>The aquaculture suffers from many challenges in order to maintain profitable activities. Among the challenges are the treats from potentially harmful natural algae blooms in the sea water surrounding the aquaculture sites. However, in order to implement efficient mitigation actions an early warning of the harmful algae bloom events are essential.</p> <p>The main objective of this study is to identify, demonstrate and validate the benefit of using satellite Earth observation information in support of the existing decision making processes for disaster management operations, and exemplified through the existing actions established for harmful algae bloom monitoring in Norwegian waters in support of the aquaculture industry. The project specifically addresses the development and implementation of a pre operational demonstration towards a sustainable service for toxic/harmful algae bloom monitoring and management decision support, related to the <i>effective management of fisheries and aquaculture, public health, and ecosystem problems related to marine biotoxins and harmful algae.</i></p> <p>The present report describes the specifications and design of the EO-based supportive service to be including in the existing HAB management structure under the authority of the Directorate of Fisheries of Norway, and under the supervision of the Institute of Marine Research.</p> <p>The service is optimised for near real-time provision of information on algae bloom events, and is based on satellite data processing and analysis from SeaWiFS and AVHRR sensors.</p>			
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1. Introduction

A national Norwegian monitoring service for harmful algae blooms (HAB) has been build up, primarily in support of the important aquaculture industry in the coastal waters. The so called ALGEINFO service is mainly operational during the main bloom season from March to October and publishes weekly its information about the algae bloom situation on a public web-site (<http://algeinfo.imr.no>). During alert bloom situation the information frequency and efforts for monitoring activities are increased, and an operational co-ordination centre is established at the Directorate of Fisheries to perform analysis of the situation, making decisions and disseminating information to the industry, the public and media (Pettersson et al., 2000a).

The current monitoring and decision making system for harmful algae bloom situation in Norwegian waters are strongly pending on early warning and efficient monitoring and predictions of eventually harmful bloom events. This can only be achieved through an efficient observational system based on an integrated approach using multiple information sources. These information sources includes the current network of 27 coastal stations for *in situ* observations, dedicated ship observations, satellite earth observation (EO) data as well as numerical predictions models for simulations of the bloom evolution (Pettersson et al, 2000b).

The capability of remote sensing based information products (pigment concentration and sea surface temperature) in combination with other observations has proven to be valuable for the early detection and monitoring of algae bloom events. However, the limitations of EO data observations with respect to among other cloud cover, algae specie discrimination, and subsurface observation capability encourage an integrated implementation strategy where the optimal information are obtained from the various information sources available (Pettersson et al., 2000b).

Activities supported by the Norwegian Space Centre in 1998, demonstrated the first direct applications of SeaWiFS satellite EO data for monitoring of a HAB situation in the Nordic waters. Near-real time SeaWiFS imagery provided an important component in the monitoring of a bloom of *Chattonella aff. verruculosa* in Danish and Norwegian waters during May, 1998. The SeaWiFS data was processed in near-real time by CCMS-PML, and made available for NERSC to provide a near real-time scientific interpretation and evaluation of the information for distribution to Institute of Marine Research (IMR) and Directorate of Fisheries (FD). The resulting *in situ* and EO data was further analysed and compared (Pettersson et al., 2000c). The SeaWiFS parameters was enhanced by the integration of *in situ* ship observations and with the coupled circulation and ecology prediction model (NORWECOM) operated by IMR for operational bloom forecasting (Skogen and Søiland, 1998). Figure 1 presents a visual comparison between the 15 May 1998 SeaWiFS imagery, shown as a colour composite and chlorophyll *a* map, and peak value chlorophyll distributions in 0-30 metre depth as obtained by R/V Dannevig during the 8-days period during 9-17 May 1998.

It appears that the early warning capability of the current monitoring system is limited due to the small number of offshore stations and the trans-boundary nature of algae bloom. A more regional approach including EO-derived environmental information may contribute achieving an earlier warning, which is necessary for successful mitigation actions. Potential benefits of including use of EO products is also acknowledged for (a) better integration of the regional dimension of the HAB, and (b) potential improvement of regional co-operation with neighbouring countries. The limitations of EO-based monitoring technology such as dependence on cloud-free conditions and inability to sub-surface monitoring is partly compensated through the integrated use with the current *in situ* based monitoring techniques. Furthermore, integration EO product with numerical forecasting model has the potential to improve the quantitative predictions of development and decay of algae blooms.

Figure 1. 15 May 1998 SeaWiFS (a) colour composite (the 555, 510 and 443 nm bands as red, green and blue respectively) and (b) chlorophyll a concentration image compared to (c) the peak value chlorophyll distributions in 0-30 metre depth as obtained by R/V Dannevig during the period from 9-17 May 1998. Imagery processed by CCMS-PML RSG and SeaWiFS imagery copyright of Orbital Imaging Corps and NASA SeaWiFS project.

These potential benefits can be regarded as sustainable since a number of spaceborne EO sensors are and will be operating during the coming years. It is foreseen that (1) the availability of data from several EO sources will stimulate competition and hopefully reduce cost in the EO data supply, as well as the generation of targeted value-added products, (2) improved sensor performances and continuous research on methods and algorithms for the applications of ocean colour data for estimation of the phytoplankton distribution, will contribute to improved future use of EO products in services for HAB monitoring. However for monitoring of HAB as required in this project, the current algorithms are applicable.

Following the studies of requirements and analysis of the current HAB monitoring system (Pettersson et al., 2000a, b), additional services based on daily analysis of ocean colour data has been developed. The two main goals of this development work has been to improve the early warning capability of the current system and provision of useful information for monitoring and prediction of bloom development and decay.

The present document describes these additional services including the introduction of use of EO data sources within the existing Norwegian command chain for monitoring of harmful algae bloom (HAB) events. The specifications of the developed service are presented in section 2. Then details on the definition and design of the different tools, methods and solutions implemented are given in section 3. A project demonstration and evaluation of the impact of the additional service you the existing HAB-management system is presented in section 4. Section 5 summarises and concludes the current report.

2. Service specification

Within the DeciDe-HAB project a pre-operational system for integrated use of EO data in the existing operational HAB command chain should be specified, designed and demonstrated. A demonstration period is scheduled from the middle of April to the end of June 2000. Near-real time EO imagery and information will be made available on a daily basis (dependant on the cloud cover conditions) for use in the monitoring of HAB events in the waters of Norwegian interest. Value-added information products will be provided for regular users and in support of the decision making process during eventual HAB situations. The additional services that are under development in the frame of the DeciDe-HAB project are intimately based on the expertise of the three project partners and their interaction with the existing HAB command chain.

A general outline of the scheme has been adopted for the EO data implementation and the associated overall information flow, will be developed in terms of four main modules (Figure 2):

1. Timely EO data acquisition and provision
2. Value-adding and HAB information extraction
3. Distribution and dissemination of service products and information
4. Interaction with and within the decision support system.

A detailed structure of the flow of information is presented in Figure 4 (section 3.1), including the role of each partner in the extended suggested monitoring service. An identification and definition of foreseen additional implementations toward the first exploitation phase is expected as a result of the experience from the demonstration project during year 2000.

Figure 2. General information flow in the DeciDe-HAB project.

2.1 The EO data Information Flow

A main constraint on the additional EO based system and service to be implemented in this project is the time delay of accessibility to user friendly information products. According to the HAB service a two days delay from the data acquisition to the delivery of information is acceptable under regular monitoring conditions. Value-added and aggregated EO information products is also essential in order to match the requirements of easy use and analysis within the existing HAB monitoring service. The staff involved in these operations has limited experience and time available to analyse and digest the additional information from the satellite EO data sources. Hence easy access and availability is essential as well as information delivery within less than 24 hours could bring a significant improvement of the existing system in term of its early warning capabilities for HAB events.

The success evaluation criteria for the implementation of the DeciDe-HAB project is pending on four main components:

1. Availability of EO data, i.e. acquisition and transmission of the data by the satellite system; real-time pre-processing and transmission of validated information products by the receiving station to the DeciDe-HAB project team.
2. Efficiency and quality of the system and information implemented within DeciDe-HAB project.
3. Appropriate definition and dissemination of the project concept, implementation and main outputs.
4. Feedback from HAB Management authorities to the DeciDe-HAB project team in terms of service evaluation and provision of *in situ* validation data.

2.1.1 The EO data Sources

The DeciDe-HAB demonstration service relies on an existing operational satellite data acquisition service performed by the satellite receiving station at the University of Dundee (Scotland) and the Center for Coastal and Marine Science/Plymouth Marine Laboratory (CCMS-PML). The latter is a partner in the project. Ocean-colour based service is based on the daily acquisition of SeaWiFS ocean-colour data from the US Orbview-2 satellite. The receiving station of the University of Dundee provides an operational service and real-time dissemination of various satellite EO data to specific value-adding entities, including the project partner CCMS-PML.

Dundee receiving station processes SeaWiFS data to level 1 (usable HDF format raw data) and the processed data is then transferred automatically to CCMS-PML, for further thematic processing. In a similar manner NOAA AVHRR data are also distributed for thematic processing and use. This so-called Level-1 data processing is usually performed within few hours after data transmission by the satellite. Most of the processing is automated in order to ensure an operational provision of data seven days a week and twenty-four hours a day.

2.1.2 EO Data Value-adding

CCMS-PML receive level-1 SeaWiFS products through a fast downlink (see section 3.1.1 for details) from Dundee. The SeaWiFS Automatic Processing System (SeaAPS) perform the processing of SeaWiFS data from level-1 to level-2 information products. A number of level-2 products, such as maps of chlorophyll concentration, attenuation coefficient, and RGB reflectance colour composite are derived by the automated processing system. Operational information maps for defined project areas are then extracted, saved as GIF image files, and put on their project specific web space at the CCMS-PML server. The SeaAPS system produce both colour GIF file for

easy and quick visual interpretation of algae bloom situation, as well as Black-and-white 8bits GIF files from which numerical values of chlorophyll concentration can be retrieved for further numerical analysis and evaluation. The entire processing chain has been automatised for operational purpose.

For the DeciDe-HAB project the geographical area extends from 02°E to 12°E, and from 52°N to 62°N (Figure 6). At this latitude the optimal SeaWiFS over-flight occurs between 11.00 AM and 14.00, with respect to the orbiting cycle. Therefore, a first analysis of daily acquisition is made available in the evening of the day of acquisition.

An automatic down-link (FTP protocol) for the level-2 products from CCMS-PML to NERSC will be established in order to disseminate the value-added information through official DeciDe-HAB web site. The EO data acquisition and automatic processing is nominally performed within less than six hours after data transmission by the satellite, allowing for analysis of the data during the evening of the day of acquisition.

A two-level analysis process will be implemented at NERSC. The first stage comprises near real-time visual analysis of the SeaWiFS level-2 data products and includes:

1. an overall evaluation of the data quality, including cloud cover detection and rejected pixels;
2. interpretation of algae bloom situation in term of chlorophyll-a pigment concentration;
3. in case of detection of high chlorophyll values, analysis of RGB composite and SST images in order to reduce ambiguity on the nature of the high pigment concentration (necessary in case II waters);
4. Generation of a short analysis report of the bloom situation that summarises the bloom situation, and which takes into account the historic development of the situations from the previous observations. The report should include identification of water masses of different origin, ocean fronts and features and the actual pigment distribution, using both SeaWiFS, AVHRR and other information sources.
5. Eventually, inform the users and the HAB command chain directly, via dedicated e-mail or telephone messages, of the detection of extensive (potentially harmful) algae blooms or other significant changes.

A second-level analysis may be undertaken in case of identified harmful algae bloom situations. This level of investigations will then include a more detailed analysis of the satellite-derived pigment concentration, synergetic analysis with other source of information (*in situ* observations, meteorological conditions, model simulations, user reports, other source of EO data, etc.). The goal of this detailed analysis is to generate an overall risk assessment map for the investigation area as well as providing direct advises for further *in situ* acquisition of information (e.g. planning of dedicated cruise activities).

2.1.3 EO data Products and Information

The service products depend upon the environmental situation, i.e. regular monitoring or emergency situation (algae bloom alert) efforts.

Different types of existing and modified products will be evaluated, which are targeted toward different group of potential users, e.g. HAB information users: HAB management authorities, aquaculture industry, monitoring scientists and public media.

However, in the context of DeciDe-HAB and of the command-chain for decision making in management of HAB in Norway, the users of the system are the Directorate of Fisheries and the Institute of Marine Research, located in both Bergen and Flødevigen. The personnel involved in

HAB management at these institutions are generally scientists and/or staff with good knowledge on environmental monitoring and data sample analysis, mainly marine biologists and oceanographers.

EO products during regular monitoring

The regular monitoring system, the direct user access and the dissemination of the standard EO products will be performed through the dedicated DeciDe-HAB web-site established at <http://www.nrsc.no/Decide-HAB>. The WWW interface provides easy access to daily AVHRR-SST and selected SeaWiFS products, and interpretation reports of the situation related to HAB. Potential users must register with the system (via a WWW page) and their details are entered into a database, which is configured to provide access to only certain areas and products.

During the project demonstration phase, the Nansen Center will perform interpretation and analysis of the EO data, and derive information products for access via the DeciDe-HAB web-site. All remote sensing products, i.e. SeaWiFS level 2 and AVHRR-SST files are split into standard Mercator-projected areas (Figure 3a shows currently active areas served by CCMS-PML for multiple applications and Figure 3b the “nw” area set up to monitor Southern Norway within DeciDe-HAB). The following EO based information products will be implemented for use:

- SeaWiFS data with a nadir spatial resolution of 1.1 km and so higher resolution satellite or airborne imagery may be useful if the bloom is relatively small or close to shore. Standard level 2 products such as:
 - chlorophyll concentration,
 - diffuse attenuation coefficient, and
 - project-specific products such as RGB colour composite of water leaving radiance at 443, 520 and 550 nm.
- AVHRR sea surface temperature images, possibly completed with ATSR data, can provide high frequency coverage, several passes per day, when these situations occur. The analysis of SST data gives insight on the main circulation patterns and water masses. This type of indirect information is valuable while giving additional environmental parameters to the interpretation of the current situation.

Generally, the expert analysis required the use of information from both the AVHRR and SeaWiFS sensors. The main product is the chlorophyll-a concentration map derived from SeaWiFS using the standard NASA SeaWiFS algorithm. However, because of the inadequacy of this algorithm for case 2 coastal water, computed high values are not necessarily the mark of an algae bloom, but may be due to the presence of other optically-active substances in the water-column. The ambiguity of high chlorophyll-concentration values may, in favourable cases, be reduced by the analysis of the water-leaving radiance spectra.

Within the DeciDe-HAB project, CCMS-PML will implement an ad-hoc product as a colour composite of the water-leaving radiances at 443, 510 and 555 nm. This specific product may be of high value to discriminate algae bloom from suspended sediment, and even different family of algae (coccolithophorid for example).

Figure 3. (a) Currently active areas in operation by CCMS-PML and (b) “nw” area set up to monitor waters of interest for Norway in 1998/9.

The role of EO products during emergency situations

During emergency bloom situations it is envisaged that the regular operational system will be running and deliver images on a daily basis (or as frequent as they are useful/cloud free), but this will be complemented by additional data sets which would come from other environmental and/or model sources.

Additionally dedicated ship observations/cruises and airborne reconnaissance, including visual observations, UV/IR scanner, Side-looking Aperture Radar (SLAR), may be initiated by the Directorate of Fisheries.

During emergency bloom situations, IMR may also perform real-time model simulations and forecasting of algae bloom development, using their combined physical ocean and marine ecosystem model (NORWECOM). For the 1998 HAB event, the model was able to forecast bloom development including the growth and movement of this large harmful algae bloom in the threatened region, up to 48 hours into the future. However, due to insufficient knowledge of the mechanisms that triggers the initiation and development of blooms, NORWECOM (as is the case with most other numerical models of this kind) is not able to predict the occurrence of a new bloom of a specific species. The interpretation of the model results is thus strongly dependent on other observations from *in situ* or EO sources to identify bloom situations.

Integration of satellite-derived bio-physical parameters, such as sea surface temperature and chlorophyll pigment concentration, with the numerical model is a way to improve the forecasting capability. Specific integrated EO information products must then be elaborate for integration within the model. In particular, DeciDe-HAB includes the possibility to deliver the derived chlorophyll distribution at model grid scale and projection. Since EO data have a much better resolution (about 1 km at nadir) than the model (20 km), optimal data smoothing may be required.

2.2 The Role of Project Participants

DeciDe-HAB is carried out by three main partners with the assistance of the national authorities in charge of harmful algae bloom management in Norway.

The Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC) is the project co-ordinator, and play the central role in the project by gathering and processing information delivered by the EO data provider (CCMS-PML) and delivering, digested and targeted information to the user partner - Institute of Marine Research (IMR) and the Directorate of Fisheries (FD) as the external to project end-user.

The main tasks of NERSC includes;

1. to analyse the products in terms of algae bloom and to deliver value-added information to the project users in an intelligible and targeted forms;
2. to daily maintain a project web site (including a public area) where the partners and a number of users of the service may access the NRT information on algae bloom situation;
3. to collect remarks and requirements from the user side (IMR and FD) and transpose those in terms of refine products requirements, which are then submit to CCMS-PML for improvement of the image products;
4. to inform directly in real-time the user panel and authorities of potential HAB events; and
5. to co-ordinate the overall activity of the project.

The main tasks of CCMS-PML includes;

1. to provide to the NERSC, SeaWiFS and AVHR-SST products adequate for HAB monitoring;
2. to ensure near real-time availability of EO data;.
3. to develop and adapt their current EO operational products to the specificity of the DeciDe-HAB project by incorporating requirements from the project.

The main tasks of IMR includes;

1. to provide feedback on and review of the service;
2. to impose constraints on additional and/or complementary information required for optimising the service;
3. to eventually run their coupled physical-ecosystem model for prediction of the development and decay of a detected HAB event; and
4. to gather *in situ* measurements acquired during field monitoring campaigns performed by IMR and FD, and make them available to the project for further validation and analysis of satellite images.

The main tasks of FD are;

1. to provide feedback on and review of the service;

3. System definition and design

In this section we describe the design structure and the main products and tools for the DeciDe-HAB service support to the existing Norwegian ALGEINFO system.

3.1 Detailed Structure and Information Flow

The identified key elements and modules of the DeciDe-HAB service is identified to include (Figure 4):

- Provision of various EO data products through the existing UK infrastructure for near real-time satellite data acquisition at the University of Dundee.
- Value-adding processing of information products, including standard SeaWiFS and AVHRR data products, dedicated product generation and expert analysis and interpretation of integrated information from EO and other data sources.
- Service provision and information products. This part of the service will be operated in various modes according to the level of operations (regular service or the two levels of emergency situations). The various products and information sources are updated regularly during the period of the services operations.
- Information dissemination and contact with the decision support system (ALGEINFO). In order to assure introduction and use of value-added EO products and information the dissemination links will be based on a we-site distribution as well as direct interaction and contacts with the personnel involved in the support system for HAB events.

3.1.1 EO data pre-processing

In the UK, special status has been granted to the National Environment Research Council (NERC) funded Dundee Satellite Receiving Station (DSRS) at the University of Dundee, Scotland. DSRS receives and archive SeaWiFS imagery over the UK and European shelf seas and north-east Atlantic Ocean. The Remote Sensing Group at the CCMS Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML) undertakes the data processing for the UK research user community, and for foreign customers under special agreement and contracts. SeaWiFS and AVHRR data are received at the UK receiving station at the University of Dundee. SeaWiFS images are converted into level 1 HDF format while AVHRR remain in the raw HRPT format and are then transferred automatically at 2 Mbit/s over the UK academic network (SuperJANET) to the remote sensing group at CCMS-PML (Figure 5). DSRS converts the raw level 0 SeaWiFS data (raw High-Resolution Picture Transmission, HRPT, format) into level 1 data (raw Hierarchical Data Format, HDF, format). These are transferred via the Internet to NASA and PML. At PML-CCMS an automated data processing system checks for the arrival of an image and starts processing usually within five minutes of pass reception.

Figure 4. Information flow and principal modules of the Decide-HAB service (red dotted area). Project actions under the responsibility of NERSC are displayed in blue, of CCMS-PML in dark green and IMR's actions in salmon-pink.

For SeaWiFS data, the processing uses a combination of the NASA SeaWiFS Data Analysis System (SeaDAS) and the SeaWiFS Automatic Processing System (SeaAPS) developed by CCMS-PML (Figure 5). The average processing time for a SeaWiFS image is approximately 120 minutes (on a dual processor Sun Ultra-2), and includes placing the final products on the World Wide Web (<http://www.npm.ac.uk/rsdas>) for immediate browsing. SeaDAS is primarily designed for processing data of the so-called Case I waters (mainly open-ocean conditions), where the optical properties are dominated by phytoplankton and associated by-products. Many European coastal waters are of the so-called Case II, where the optical properties are determined by either suspended particulate material (SPM) or coloured dissolved organic material (CDOM), and frequently by a combination of SPM, CDOM and phytoplankton. SeaAPS has additional atmospheric correction algorithms, specifically designed for SPM dominated “bright pixel” waters where the near-infra red water-leaving radiance can no longer be taken as negligible and the Case I atmospheric correction (dark pixel) method fails (Moore *et al.* 1999).

Atmospherically corrected level 1 data are used to produce level-2 biological and geophysical products: water-leaving radiance at five visible wavebands (412, 443, 490, 510 and 555 nm); derived products including chlorophyll *a* concentration, Coastal Zone Color Scanner (CZCS)-type pigment concentration, diffuse attenuation coefficient at 490 nm, several atmospheric parameters determined during the atmospheric correction procedure (Moore *et al.*, 1999).

In summary, the PML-CCMS SeaWiFS processing follows the following pathway (Lavender and Groom, 1999):

- Data extraction of individual bands.
- Geolocation uses an orbital model and GPS data from the on-board GPS system.
- Navigation adjustment by automatic location of ‘ground control points’ to check residual navigation errors.
- Calibration of visible bands is followed by calculation of water leaving radiance and biological or physical quantities, such as chlorophyll concentration or attenuation at 490nm (see section 3.2.1).
- Mapping of images to pre-selected geographical areas specified in a database with added latitude/longitude marks, annotation, temperature scale etc..
- Production of images in GIF or TIF format and storage on the WWW server.

Contemporary Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) Sea Surface Temperature (SST) data, obtained from the DSRS, are processed and “integrated” with the SeaWiFS imagery. The PANORAMA software used to process the AVHRR imagery (Miller *et al.* 1997) has been in operation for several years, with the combined ocean colour and SST products being of value to many areas of oceanographic research by providing near simultaneous observation of surface biological and physical processes. This combination acts as a precursor to data from satellites such as the European Space Agency’s ENVISAT mission, due for launch summer 2001, which will have sensors onboard for both the ocean colour (Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer, MERIS, with 15 spectral bands and 300 m spatial resolution) and temperature (Advanced Along-Track Scanning Radiometer, AATSR). In addition also the microwave Advanced Synthetic Aperture Radar (ASAR – X-band, 30 m resolution) will cover within the swath of the optical instruments.

The procedures for AVHRR are described in Miller *et al.* 1997. AVHRR data processing follows a pathway similar to SeaWiFS’s with following differences:

1. Geolocation using an orbital model (SGP) with NORAD two-line element ephemeris

2. Calibration of infra-red bands, conversion to brightness temperature and calculation of sea-surface temperature using standard NOAA algorithms (described in section 3.2.1).

Figure 5. The information flow in the CCMS-PML SeaWiFS Automatic Processing System (SeaAPS) used in this DeciDe-HAB project.

3.1.2 Near-real time access

The data processing described above is usually completed within two hours of data reception at CCMS-PML. AVHRR data have no restriction on use whereas SeaWiFS is operated on a commercial basis with near-real time access restricted to users who have received specific non-commercial use authorisation from NASA. This is usually for support of research cruises providing SeaWiFS calibration/validation or demonstration pre-operational projects.

In DeciDe-HAB, near-real time access to AVHRR and SeaWiFS data is provided through the NERSC web site (<http://www.nrsdc.no/Decide-HAB>), which is password protected to restrict access to SeaWiFS images to project users who are authorised by NASA. Only SeaWiFS Authorised

Research Users are permitted to access SeaWiFS ocean colour data. All data are subject to a 14-day embargo, unless specifically approved by NASA for near-real time research usage. The DeciDe-HAB project has been granted near-real time access to SeaWiFS data for the demonstration phase period. The web-site access control system is designed so that access to specific data has to be granted as opposed to restricting access to specific data.

3.2 Value Adding Functions

3.2.1 Retrieval of Geophysical Parameters

Ocean colour

Ocean colour is governed by the optical properties of seawater together with suspended particles (organic and inorganic) and coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM). Phytoplankton absorb sunlight, required for photosynthesis, through pigments with 95% of the light absorbed by chlorophyll-a, b, c, photosynthetic carotenoids (PSC) and photoprotectant carotenoids (PPC) which are grouped together as the total pigments (Aiken *et al.*, 1995). As the phytoplankton concentration increases the reflectance in the blue decreases (due to the absorption of chlorophyll-like pigments over a broad wavelength band) and the green increases slightly, and a ratio of blue to green water reflectance can be used to derive quantitative estimates of pigment concentration (Clarke *et al.*, 1970). CDOM reduces the reflectance as it causes significant absorption in the ultraviolet and blue wavelengths relative to those in the red. Suspended particulate matter (SPM) enhances reflectance because of the particle backscattering that is inversely related to wavelength, being strong in the blue and then decreasing in influence through the spectrum.

The IOCCG Working Group (1998) recommended that a chlorophyll retrieval algorithm for satellite EO data should utilise wavebands at 555 or 560 nm and 443 nm and an additional waveband at 410 nm to account for CDOM absorption. The Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor (SeaWiFS) uses an algorithm based on the 490/555 band ratio and a cubic polynomial fit based on the SeaWiFS Bio-optical Algorithm Mini-workshop (O'Reilly *et al.*, 1998). The 490/555 ratio is used, rather than the 443/555 ratio, as it is more linear in log-log space when compared to chlorophyll-a. This is because the CDOM absorption is lower at 490 compared to 443 and there is usually a strong correlation between the chlorophyll-a and carotenoids, which are the main absorbing pigments at 490 nm, (Aiken *et al.*, 1995). The coefficients have since been updated, due to the addition of data sets, and the current algorithm is called Ocean Chlorophyll 2 version 2 (OC2-v2), see equations 1 and 2. This may shortly be replaced by OC2-v3, see equation 3, which has additional data from chlorophyll-rich (greater than 10 mg.m⁻³) waters (O'Reilly *et al.*, 1999).

$$X = \log_{10} \frac{R_{rs}(490)}{R_{rs}(555)} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{OC2-v2 } chl = 10^{(0.2974 - 2.2429X + 0.8358X^2 - 0.0077X^3)} - 0.0929 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{OC2-v3 } chl = 10^{(0.2773 - 2.3534X + 1.1416X^2 - 0.2972X^3)} - 0.0788 \quad (3)$$

Inverse or semi-analytical radiance modelling is a method for detecting and separating different substances from multi-channel measurements using a radiative transfer model based on known absorption and scattering relationships. This approach has been adopted for processing of the

ENVISAT MERIS data in coastal regions (Attema *et al.*, 1998). Schiller and Doerffer (1999) use a neural network as a multiple non-linear regression technique, to parameterise the inverse relationship between concentrations and reflectances, which produces estimates of chlorophyll, CDOM and SPM concentrations.

The MERIS sensor has also a relatively narrow waveband located at 682.5 nm to detect the solar stimulated chlorophyll fluorescence peak (Rast *et al.*, 1999), which is linked to the phytoplankton concentration but also to the actual cell physiology and can also vary with the nutrient status, species composition and growth rate. Gower and Borstad (1990) demonstrated the possibility of remotely sensing this peak using the airborne Fluorescence Line Imager, an airborne imaging spectrometer (Borstad *et al.*, 1985). The method for use of the fluorescence signal for the MERIS band set is presented in Gower *et al.* (1999).

Sea-surface temperature

SST images are produced from AVHRR using the global operational equations published by NOAA (Kidwell 1995). These are based on earlier work by McClain *et al.* (1985) on the split-window technique, which makes use of the difference in atmospheric absorption at two infrared wavelengths. The current formulations are called non-linear sea-surface temperature (NLSST) equations:

$$SST = aT_4 + bT_{sfc}(T_4 - T_5) + c(T_4 - T_5)(\sec \text{sza} - 1) + d$$

where T_4 and T_5 are the brightness temperatures in AVHRR channels 4 and 5, sza is the satellite zenith angle (relative to the pixel position on the Earth's surface), and T_{sfc} is a prior estimate of SST, which is taken from the simpler multi-channel sea-surface temperature (MCSST) equation. The coefficients a to d are calculated empirically by NOAA using match-ups between buoy measurements and satellite overpasses. The sensitivity of AVHRR radiometers is approximately 0.1 °C, and the published absolute accuracy of NLSST estimates is 0.6 °C root mean square difference from *in situ* measurements.

Standard methods for calculating SST magnify the noise inherent in brightness temperature data, by multiplying the difference between channels. A modification called *partial SST*, involves splitting the standard SST equation into 'sea' and 'atmosphere' components, and smoothing only the atmosphere component (Miller *et al.*, 1997); this considerably reduces noise without blurring image structures.

3.2.2 Evaluation, interpretation and analysis

The region of the DeciDe-HAB monitoring has been geographically divided into seven sub-regions: Kattegatt, East Skagerrak, West Skagerrak, West Jutland, Hordaland, North Sea, and south-west Norway (Figure 6). For each zone, a brief description of the algae bloom situation is given, taking into account the information gained from the images of the day, as well as the recent history of processes and events in the area and the information from *in situ* field data and observations.

The daily analysis required the use of images from SeaWiFS and AVHRR EO sources. The main source remains chlorophyll-a concentration maps derived from SeaWiFS using the standard NASA SeaWiFS algorithm, and complemented by the analysis of water-leaving radiance spectra in order to reduce the false-alarm rate in case II waters.

The analysis of SST data gives insight on the main circulation patterns and water masses of various origin.

In case of regular monitoring, conclusions of the analysis of the various EO and non-EO data sources are also provided in a short descriptive text, which in wording summarises the bloom

situation in the region and facilitate the own interpretation of the non-experts.

Figure 6. Geographical sectors of the project area in which a simplified colour code is used to characterise the algae bloom situation.

3.3 The User Interface

The DeciDe-HAB project has implemented a web-based browser system for the delivery of information on algae bloom situation in near real-time (typically four to ten hours after the acquisition of the satellite data).

The web-site (<http://www.nrsc.no/Decide-HAB>) is the main user interface to the information provided by the DeciDe-HAB service. In case of detection of potential harmful bloom events active and direct communication will be initialised, following the structure implemented in the national contingency plan for handling of emergency situations in the coastal zone (Anon., 2000).

The web-site includes five main areas, which can be access through the web-site front-page (Figure 7), some areas has open availability and some are password protected and available for project accredited users:

1. The general project description area, including the project objectives, partnership, promotional information, press-releases, project funding, etc. (Figure 7).
2. The public daily information on oceanographic situation in the monitored area (Figure 8). This information includes selected AVHRR-SST images of the day and a short text analysis of the situation, based on all available information. A link to the SST image time series archive is proposed, as well as a link to the SeaWiFS daily report page (restricted access).
3. The project-restricted area for daily information on algae bloom situation (Figure 9). The daily updated web-page includes a selection of SeaWiFS products relevant for algae bloom analysis, i.e., chlorophyll-a concentration and RGB colour composite of water-leaving radiances, and an analysis of the situation as a analysis of the bloom situation. Information on previous situation can be browsed through a link to the SeaWiFS image archive organised in monthly batches.
4. The project-restricted area for archive, time series and dynamical analysis of bloom events (Figure 10). The archive area gives access to daily AVHRR-SST, and SeaWiFS chlorophyll and RGB images acquired during the project period (March to July, 2000) for the two last years (1998 and 1999). A system of graphical links through an intuitive design allows the user to navigate through the time series of products (Figure 11), and then to retrieve the information pertaining to a specific day (Figure 9).
5. The modelling area (Figure 12) gathers the main results of simulations and prediction of HAB development, performed by IMR using the 3-D coupled physical-ecosystem model for the North Sea region (NORWECOM).

Figure 8 shows the WWW page, which displays the daily AVHRR-SST images graphically to the user and gives an indication of the cloud cover (percentage of valid pixels). The user can then navigate into the SeaWiFS link and enter the project restricted area (Figure 9), which displays the appropriate ocean colour based products and the information resulting from the analysis of the HAB situation. Within both the AVHRR-SST viewer and SeaWiFS viewer, the user can access the time series for the current year by following the link to the archive (Figure 10). There the user can navigate through the images by going to specific dates or using the previous/next buttons if a time-series of image products is to be viewed (Figure 11).

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Welcome to the home page of

DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Latest Updated Situation (daily information)

[Public Area](#)

Press Release

[\(in Norwegian\)](#)

[Numerical Simulation &
Forecasting](#)

ALGEINFO

The direct link to the official Harmful Algae Bloom Monitoring service of Norway

This research project is sponsored by the
[European Space Agency](#)

and
[Norwegian Space Centre](#)

co-ordinated by the [Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center](#)

Project coordinator: [Lasse H. Petterson, NERSC](#), Bergen, Norway.

With the collaboration of

[CCMS-PML, UK](#)

[Institute of Marine Research, Norway](#)

Last updated 02 June 2000 by [Dominique Durand](#).

Figure 7: Home page of the DeciDe-HAB web-site (<http://www.nrsc.no/Decide-HAB>).

<p>Welcome to DeciDe-HAB's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak</p> <p>Decide-HAB is a R&D demonstration project with objective to improve near real-time collection of field observations of Harmful Algae Blooms (HAB) in Norwegian and neighbouring waters.</p> <p>The below satellite image (NOAA AVHRR) shows the Sea Surface Temperature (SST) information, indicating the different water masses present in the region.</p>	
<p>Friday, 12 May 2000</p>	
<p>Sea Surface Temperature</p> <p><i>click on the image to enlarge</i></p> <p>Land and clouds in black</p>	<p>Evaluation of the situation as of: 12/5/2000 Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W</p> <p>Comments :</p> <p>The bloom along west Jutland is still observed extending with a highly visible surface signature (red colours) from the German Bight and almost north to Skagen.</p> <p>See most recent satellite-derived chlorophyll concentrations (restricted access) for more information.</p>
<p>Earlier Situation</p>	<p>Enter Decide-HAB restricted area</p>
<p>Part of the satellite information provided through the project is restricted, due to Copyright regulations.</p> <p>A temporary access can be granted to people involved in HAB-monitoring and field data collection.</p> <p>Contact Dominique Durand to get a password. Please give a short description of your main motivations for accessing this site.</p> <p><small>The authorization access to this site can be changed without notification.</small></p>	

Figure 8. The public area displaying daily AVHRR-SST images and a short descriptive analysis the water masses identified in the region and their possible advection from previous observations, as well as the algae bloom situation.

DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

All SeaWiFS images and data presented on this website are for *research and education* use only.

All commercial use of SeaWiFS data must be coordinated with [ORBIMAGE](#)

Friday, 12 May 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

The research use of this image is restricted to NASA SeaWiFS authorized users. Please respect this restriction.

Copyright NASA SeaWiFS Project / Orbimage Corp.

Evaluation of the situation as of: 12/5/2000

Product : SeaWiFS chlor_a
Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N
Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W
Using climatological ancillary data
Valid pixels: %

Comments :
 Somewhat higher pigment concentration levels are observed in the entire bloom area of the west Jutland bloom as compared to May 11 and 10.. Is the bloom taking up again?. The lower pigment concentrations in central Skagerrak today reaches the area between Skagen and Larvik, most likely associated with inflow of North Sea water into the central Skagerrak (blue color). Analyzing the RGB image ("true color composite") resolves a brighter surface reflection indicating that a bloom of Coccothlorophorids may be under development in this region - i.e. in the water masses of North Sea origin flowing into the Skagerrak region. Higher pigment concentrations (red and yellow colors) is confined to an area (up 5-10 km off shore), except for some further off shore plumes (off Stavanger, Arendal, Kristiansand and Lista), along the coast of south Norway from the Swedish border north to Fedje. The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds (only a few areas in the northern part of the image) or saturated data.
 The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

Look [here](#) for previous dates.

This Web-site is maintained by [Dominique Durand](#), NERSC

Figure 9. Restricted-to-project web-area, displaying daily SeaWiFS level 2 products (chlorophyll concentration on the left and reflectance RGB composite on the right), and descriptive analysis report of the algae bloom situation.

Browsing: /SeaWiFS/2000

← [Parent] [1998] [1999] [Today]

Chl-a April	SST April
Chl-a May	SST May
Chl-a June	SST June
Chl-a July	SST July

[Dominique Durand](#)
 Last modified: Mon May 8 11:27:15 MET DST 2000

Figure 10. Main entrance to the project time-series archive of SeaWiFS and AVHRR-SST products.

Browsing: /SeaWiFS/2000/May

All SeaWiFS images and data presented on this website are for *research and education* use only.

All commercial use of SeaWiFS data must be coordinated with [ORBIMAGE](#)

← [Parent] [1998] [1999] [Previous] [Next] [Today] [SST Archive]

SeaWiFS chlorophyll-a products - May 2000

Click on the image for A4 size

01 May 2000	02 May 2000	03 May 2000	04 May 2000	05 May 2000	06 May 2000	07 May 2000	08 May 2000
09 May 2000	10 May 2000	11 May 2000	12 May 2000	13 May 2000	14 May 2000	15 May 2000	16 May 2000
17 May 2000	18 May 2000	19 May 2000	20 May 2000	21 May 2000	22 May 2000	23 May 2000	24 May 2000
		No Image Available					
25 May 2000	26 May 2000	27 May 2000	28 May 2000	29 May 2000	30 May 2000	31 May 2000	
No Image Available							

Figure 11. Time series of maps of SeaWiFS-derived chlorophyll concentration for the month of May 1998, as available through the restricted area of the DeciDe-HAB web-site. Each image gives direct access back to the daily images and report from the various days.

Modeling the development of Harmful Algae Blooms A part of the "DeciDe" Project

9 May 2000

The work presented here is part of the European Space Agency project, "DeciDe for Near Real-time use of Ocean Color Data in Hazard Management of Toxic Algae Blooms". The simulations producing the presented results were run using a coupled physical-biological model (NORWECOM) at the Institute of Marine Research. NORWECOM is used here to predict the development and transport of the harmful algae blooms in Norwegian and northern European waters.

For further information on satellite observations of harmful algae blooms and the DeciDe project, please contact [Lasse Pettersson](#) or [Dominique Durand](#).

For more information on distribution of harmful algae off Norway, see <http://algeinfo.imr.no/>.

Summary

The images presented here show first results from modelling simulations of a harmful algae bloom (HAB) presently along the coast of Denmark and in the Skagerrak. The bloom of the flagellate, *Chattonella* sp., was first observed by satellite off the western coast of Denmark on about 18 April. The model used to produce these images was initialized from data from 18 and 19 April and indicates that as of 8 May the highest concentrations of flagellates (dominated by *Chattonella* sp.) at a depth of 3 m are still located primarily along the coast of Denmark. A high-concentration band extends also from the northern tip of Denmark westward through the Skagerrak. The overall distribution of the HAB corresponds well with satellite observations of distributions for sea-surface temperature and chlorophyll. The simulation also indicates that nitrate in surface waters may be strongly depleted by the growth of the bloom. Based on the weather forecast for the area, the forecast for HAB development indicates that the bloom shall be in a phase of decline by 16 May and does not present an immediate threat to aquaculture installations along the southern coast of Norway. The situation shall be followed closely until the bloom has subsided.

Simulation of flagellate carbon biomass
showing results for a depth of 3 m for the dates 21 April, 8 May and 16 May

Simulation of nitrate concentration
showing results for a depth of 3 m for the dates 21 April, 8 May and 16 May

Figure 12. The model result web-area displays of simulations and forecasting of the development of identified HAB events. The upper time series shows the growth and decay of the *Chattonella* bloom (concentration of flagellate in $\text{mg N}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) between April 12 and May 16, as predicted by the NORWECOM models. The model was initiated by SeaWiFS –derived chlorophyll concentration as observed in the image of April 19. The lower time-series shows the predicted decay of nitrate between the same period of time, producing a limitation in nutrient supply and hence the decay of the bloom. Information and modelling results of this kind is only made available in case of identified HAB situations, i.e. under the various higher levels of alert situations.

3.4 Suggested Interactions with the Existing Service

Today, regular monitoring of algae and harmful algae blooms (HABs) is conducted at 27 stations along the Norwegian coast and reported to the general public in the ALGEINFO web-site administered by IMR (their research facility in Flødevigen, Norway). This monitoring service is a joint effort by more than seven institutions and companies in various parts of Norway. The main objective of the monitoring program is to provide an early warning of algae blooms that may be a threat to the Norwegian marine aquaculture industry. The service can be publicly accessed at <http://algeinfo.imr.no>.

Once per week and during emergency situations, regular monitoring and reporting of data at ALGEINFO is conducted from March to October and every two weeks thereafter until winter, when the probability for the development HABs along the Norwegian coast is neglectable and no updating is required. The information on algae distribution and concentrations reported in ALGEINFO is for plankton species potentially causing harmful algae blooms (HABs), as described in detail in the DeciDe-HAB Requirements document (Pettersson *et al.*, 2000a). Sampling, identification and quantification of algae are conducted by Norwegian governmental organisations (Directorate of Fisheries, the Institute of Marine Research, the Norwegian Institute for Water Research, and the State Food Control Authority) and a private consultant company (OCEANOR AS).

In the ALGEINFO web-site there exist links to web-sites with relevant additional information. One such link is to a web-site providing advice on the risk of mussel toxicity (<http://www.snt.no/nytt/blaskjell>). Information at the latter web-site is also available on a “mussel-phone” or on text-TV (Norwegian Broadcasting). The basis for the advice is primarily data on the occurrence of potentially toxic phytoplankton obtained from analysis of water samples and mussels in various regions along the coast. Established levels of warning for selected toxic algae provide criteria for recommendations.

3.4.1 HAB emergency situations and modelling

When a HAB situation is identified in Norwegian waters, dedicated efforts have often been made to map the bloom, including its propagation and transport with surface currents. This has most often involved field observations with dedicated research vessels, airplanes, satellite data and forecasting by models. Most ecosystem models include only a few functional groups of algae and the model developed and used by IMR, the NORwegian Ecological Model system (NORWECOM), includes two such functional groups of algae species - diatoms and flagellates. Due to lack of knowledge of what triggers harmful blooms NORWECOM is not able to predict the occurrence of new blooms of a specific species, and thus the results and interpretation of the model results is strongly dependent on *in situ* observations. This was the case in May 1998 during the *Chattonella aff. verruculosa* bloom in the North Sea and Skagerrak, during which time NORWECOM was run in real time and was used as one of several tools in the predictions of the bloom development. The model results were very useful in combination with *in situ* observations and EO satellite data. Importantly, the model was able to forecast bloom development including the growth and movement of this large harmful algae bloom in the threatened region 48 hours into the future. The model simulations are only initiated in connection with potential emergency situations, and the results were generally not available to the public or the aquaculture industry, but mainly used internally within the monitoring team to provide better guidance.

3.4.2 Modifications to the ALGEINFO service for the DeciDe-HAB Project

The role of ALGEINFO with respect to the distribution of information is instrumental, as described

above. It is particularly noteworthy that in an emergency situation, ALGEINFO can represent a hub for the rapid dissemination of support-related information. For example, EO products and derived information in the form of graphic, numerical and text presentations of actual bloom distribution is made available by Internet link to DeciDe-AHB web-site at NERSC. Furthermore, forecasting of HAB development may be graphically illustrated and made available to the public and/or authorities via a link to separate web-site at IMR and/or NERSC.

It is suggested that the ALGEINFO web-site (administered at the IMR research facility in Flødevigen) establish a link to the EO satellite data / images web-site at NERSC, as well as to another IMR server (in Bergen) to access views of model simulations of the development of harmful algae blooms. Thus, end users of the web-site may view actual EO images of algae bloom development and prognoses of the spread and development of the blooms.

3.4.3 Interface with current decision support procedures

The Directorate of Fisheries in Norway has the primary responsibility for monitoring harmful algae blooms and providing warning and advice during HABs along the Norwegian coast. The Directorate of Fisheries has developed an emergency-response plan (Anon., 2000) with three-level action according to the HAB situation. The plan defines operational responses and lines of command and communication (on internal, national and communal levels, and to the marine aquaculture industry, fisheries authorities, the press, etc.), for each level of response.

Primary contact person at the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries:

3. Ragnar Sanbæk, Chief Officer, responsible for the contingency plan for the coastal zone.
4. Gunnar Larsen, advisor, fisheries office, Fredrikstad.

The Institute of Marine Research, although responsible for monitoring the algae situation in the shelf and open-ocean waters, is not the responsible organisation for coastal monitoring of HABs but rather has a supporting role during HAB situations. This role may be in the form of special cruises to HAB area, modelling of the HAB development and transport, and other supporting actions. At the Institute of Marine Research, specific contact persons are to be notified during HAB situations. These persons are:

Primary contact person at IMR:

1. Hein Rune Skjoldal, Science Director, Division of Marine Environment, Bergen

Secondary contact persons at IMR:

2. Francisco Rey, Senior Researcher (phytoplanktologist), Division of Marine Environment, Bergen
3. Jan Aure, Senior Researcher (monitoring, physical oceanographer), Division of Marine Environment, Bergen
4. Einar Dahl, Senior Researcher (phytoplanktologist), Research Facility in Flødevigen.

Interfacing between IMR and the Fisheries Directorate has usually been good in the past, although room for improvement in the rapidity of communication and dissemination of information exists.

4. Demonstration scenario

For purposes of the project demonstration phase, ALGEINFO shall set up a link to the official DeciDe-HAB project web site at Nansen Center (<http://www.nrsc.no/Decide-HAB>). The DeciDe-Hab web site would show satellite-based maps of chlorophyll concentration, sea surface temperature and reflectance colour composite in the North Sea and Skagerrak, as well as prediction information obtained from the forecasting model (NORWECOM), risk assessment maps derived either from the solely analysis of the ocean-colour data set, or from a combined analysis of satellite images, *in situ* observations and model simulations. The site will also maintain an archive of SeaWiFS and AVHRR derived maps starting in 1998.

Most likely, for the demonstration we would use images and model simulations from the *Chattonella aff. verruculosa* bloom in 1998. However, a near real-time acquisition and analysis of SeaWiFS data will be conducted during the blooming period – from mid-April to mid-July - in 2000. In case of HAB event in spring/summer 2000, the demonstration will directly use near real-time data.

Between April 15 and June 30, 2000, daily acquisition, processing, evaluation, analysis and interpretation of SeaWiFS and AVHRR-SST data will be conducted. The official DeciDe-HAB web site will be consequently daily updated, and will provide public (non-restricted) information of algae bloom situation through risk assessment map and analysis reports, and restricted access to SeaWiFS data products. The demonstration which need not last more than a few days but may be operable for longer for use by the developers of the service.

4.1 User Evaluation and validation activities

During the demonstration period, a panel of evaluators (shall assess the service and report to the DeciDe-HAB steering committee. The outcome of this evaluation shall help to determine whether the modifications shall become permanent features of the HAB monitoring activities. Only each member of the panel and the DeciDe developers shall have access to the demonstration web-site links via a password-protected page. As stated above, the linked DeciDe-HAB site should serve to distribute:

- a) EO information- NERSC and CCMS-PML shall prepare and make available EO data / images at the official DeciDe-HAB web-site at NERSC.
- b) modelling information- IMR shall provide an IMR web-page for access to modelling results for harmful algae blooms;

The persons permitted to access the DeciDe demonstration web-site during an extended period of development and demonstration shall be the DeciDe project staff:

1. NERSC: Lasse Pettersson and Dominique Durand
2. PML: Steve Groom and Samantha Lavender
3. IMR: Thomas Noji, Henrik Søyland and Tor Birkeland (ALGEINFO administrator).

In addition, we shall ask following persons to evaluate the DeciDe-HAB service. Thus, they also shall have access to the DeciDe demonstration web-sites during the period of demonstration, with the aim of receiving from them an evaluation of the system:

In Norway:

- Aqua Farms AS: S. Lofnes
- Directorate of Fisheries: Ragnar Sandbæk , Gunnar Larsen

- IMR: H.R. Skjoldal, E. Svendsen, E. Dahl
- ESA-ESRIN: P. Regner, L. Fusco
- Norwegian Space Centre: G. Dahle-Strøm
- Norwegian Navy Educational Center (KNMT): S. Otto Hole
- Norwegian Institute of Water Research (NIVA): T. Johnsen
- Norwegian State Pollution Control Authority (SFT): P.E. Iversen
- Norwegian Fishermen's Organisation ("Fiskarlaget"): K. Grundvig
- KIMO: A. Fotland
- World Wildlife Fund (WWF): S. Christiansen

In other European countries:

- German Aerospace Research Center (DLR), Remote Sensing Technology Institute - Section Marine Remote Sensing, Germany: M. Hetscher,
- Bioconsult, AS, Denmark: P. Andersen
- Risoe National Laboratory, Denmark: Ch. Bay Hasager
- Danish Institute for Fisheries Research, Denmark: H. Thomsen
- Office for Environmental Protection – Fisheries Unit, Sweden: Karin Pettersson
- Ecole des Mines de Paris - Remote Sensing and Modelling Group, France: L. Wald

as well as representatives from:

- Norwegian Seafood Export Council
- NFR (Norwegian National Research Council),
- NMR (Nordic Council of Ministers)

We recognise that each person with permission to access the DeciDe web-sites showing satellite data / images must have authorisation from NASA to use SeaWiFS data. This will be arranged by NERSC and PML, once the list of Demonstration-Phase developers and evaluators is confirmed.

At the end of the demonstration period, each evaluator shall be expected to provide a review of the service. A reviewer meeting will be organised during early fall 2000 to collect the evaluation information to be reporting later on in the Evaluation Document.

During the demonstration of the DeciDe-HAB element of the ALGEINFO service, interfacing with the current decision support procedure shall also be evaluated, including:

- 1) ALGEINFO web-site accessibility
- 2) DeciDe demonstration web-sites accessibility
- 3) Quality and timeliness of the presented information
- 4) Usefulness of and suggestions for modifications to the information presented
- 5) Strengths and weaknesses of the service
- 6) Recommendations for service improvements
- 7) Suggestions for a wider dissemination strategy

In addition, a direct surveillance of the accesses made to the web-site will be performed, generating statistics on number of access, origin of the access by country and type of server, etc..

5. Summary and Conclusions

This document describes the specifications, definition and design of the EO-based supportive service to be included within the existing Norwegian HAB management structure under the authority of the Directorate of Fisheries and the supervision of the Institute of Marine Research.

Early warning of potential harmful algae blooms is crucial for an efficient monitoring system, which is needed to implement efficient mitigation actions in order to save values. The trans-boundary nature of development of HAB as well as the lack of regular off-shore observations are limiting factors of the efficiency of the current monitoring system. The international co-operations in exchange of information on development of HAB events is not very well developed and the national interests in such events is significantly different due to the various national or local activities in the coastal zone. In this respect use of EO based information sources may contribute to a better integration of the trans-boundary nature of HAB events and to improve the international co-operations.

Several EO sensor systems may provide information relevant to HAB events, either with information on parameters that are directly related to the bloom (chlorophyll concentration) or more indirectly related to the oceanographic or meteorological environmental conditions. The directly relevant EO information is the pigment concentration or solar irradiance derived from ocean colour data and the sea surface temperature from e.g. the NOAA AVHRR sensor. More indirect information, such as the radar back-scatter signature, from e.g. the ERS-2 Synthetic Aperture radar (SAR) sensor, are related to the current shear zones, ocean fronts, surface wind, surface film or surfactants etc. may also provide useful information. Due to the various limiting factors for the information from the various EO sensors, i.e. cloud cover limitations for optical ocean colour sensors, also other sources of information should be available in the interpretation process. However, in this project the most direct and useful EO based information source is the ocean colour data from currently the SeaWiFS sensor, which also will be available from several launched or scheduled optical sensors, such as MODIS and MERIS on respectively US Terra and ESA ENVISAT missions.

In order to make integrated use of the information from EO sensors and other sources four key modules of implementation were identified:

1. Timely EO data acquisition and provision
2. Value-adding and HAB information extraction
3. Distribution and dissemination of service products and information
4. Interaction with and within the decision support system.

Within these four main modules the following key elements are evaluated as necessary for its successful implementation and operations.

EO data acquisition and provision: The service will need near real-time provision of information on algae bloom events, and will be based on satellite data processing and integrated analysis of EO data from SeaWiFS and AVHRR sensors. A main constraint on the system and service to be implemented will be the delay of availability to the information, which must stay under a limit of two days from the data acquisition to the delivery of information. However, information delivery within less than 24 hours should bring a significant improvement of the system in term of early warning. A streamlined and applicable access to these two types of EO data have been built up based on the UK research satellite receiving station at the University of Dundee in Scotland. Both SeaWiFS and AVHRR data are daily automatically acquired, pre-processed (Level-1) and

transferred through a fast down-link to the Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service at CCMS-PML within a few hours after data acquisition.

Value-adding and HAB information extraction: At CCMS-PML, the SeaWiFS Automatic Processing System (SeaAPS) is in operation providing data to the UK and European research community. This system uses state of the art SeaWiFS processing algorithms to automatic generation and web-site distribution of Level-2 EO products. These Level-2 products, mainly graphical image (GIF files) products, are placed on user defined web-sites for approved research users access and down-load.

For the Decide-HAB project a dedicated user area is generated at the CCMS-PML server, where data from the geographically limited investigation area will be extracted, processed and made available through a fast down-link to NERSC. The current processing is mainly based on the standard NASA SeaDAS software for atmospheric corrections and other Level-2 products. These products includes: (i) normalised water leaving radiance at the various SeaWiFS bands, (ii) aerosol radiance and (iii) attenuation depth, (iv) colour coded chlorophyll pigment concentrations image based on various algorithms also including a cloud mask, (v) a RGB “true” visible colour composite and (vi) in-water diffuse attenuation coefficient at 490 nm. The absolute accuracy of these algorithms are well documented to be both uncertain and with significant geographical variations. Significant scientific efforts are made “world-wide” to improve the general and regional algorithms of improved absolute values in the derived information. In particular this is true for the coastal so-called Case-II waters where other coloured substances, such a dissolved organic matter and sediments are present, and significant absolute errors are documented in the derived quantities. Using human expert interpretation and regional knowledge the standard satellite-based information products (from both SeaWiFS and AVHRR) will be evaluated and interpreted before the aggregated information is presented for the HAB monitoring command chain. Mainly the information extraction will be about possible new algae blooms observed, significant changes in the overall oceanic circulation pattern of different water masses and tracing the development of already identified (harmful) algae blooms. In particular identification of areas in which blooms of coccolithophorids or flagellates are dominating is possible through the interpretation of the visible (“true” colours) channels of both SeaWiFS and/or AVHRR data. The presentation of the information will be done through a project web-site (<http://www.nrsc.no/Decide-HAB>) where a daily updated written report addresses the present situation and changes during the last days with respect to algae bloom situation. In addition also selected EO images products will be shown to support and illustrate the report given. These images will make use of the state-of-the-art Level-2 image products as well as by new tailored information products (images) modified in order to more optimally meet the users information needs. An archive of the observations from previous days/months, including the written reports and image products, will be available in order to illustrate and document the changes observed in the region.

Distribution and dissemination of service products and information: The main user interface to the information provided by the DeciDe-HAB service will be the web-based system for the delivery of information on algae bloom situation in near real-time (typically four to ten hours after data acquisition). As mentioned above the web-site will include daily and historical data and products, daily analysis report of the bloom situations over the monitored area. In addition results of numerical simulations and forecasting in case of emergency situation and eventual press releases will be distributed through the project web-site. A pre-operational system will run from mid-April to at least the end of June, 2000 and produce near-real time imagery on a daily basis (the applicability will of course be dependant on the cloud cover situation). Value-added information products and reports will be provided for regular users and in support of the decision making process during eventual HAB situations.

Interaction with and within the decision support system: The Directorate of Fisheries have

developed and implemented a contingency plan for emergency situations in the coastal zone. Through this plan and in committed agreement with the Directorate and the Institute of Marine Research certain key-personnel are identified who will be alerted through telephone and e-mail contacts in case of identified possible and significant changes in the algae bloom situation in the waters of Norwegian concern. This direct contact for evaluation of the situation is needed in order to assure an evaluation and eventual initiation of other means of observations related to possible changes in the algae bloom situations, including allocations of dedicated vessels for *in situ* identifications and mapping of possible harmful algae bloom situations. Personal, direct and committed contacts with the key-responsible staff in the current hazard command-chain is essential for a successful implementation of use of EO data in the existing service.

In addition to the use of information from EO sources for in the decision command chain the use of numerical prediction models for simulations of the blooms development is a tool under significant scientific development. The state-of-the-art ocean ecosystem models are in general able to simulate the development and decay of algae blooms due to the gradually changes in processes such as the availability of solar radiation, mixed layer depth variations, wind forcing and availability of nutrients in the water. However, these models are in general not capable of accurately reproduce the precise quantities and locations of bloom patterns, nor are they able to correctly predict the initiation of a particular algae bloom in either time or space. To improve the capabilities of these models in this respect, external information is needed in order to trigger the model representation of the bloom initiation and its development in time and space. The use of EO based information about possible blooms and their development in this respect may be very useful for the improvement of the model predictions of the development of identified bloom situations. Tailored information products will hence be developed during the course of the demonstration project.

Making integrated EO based information available along these lines will be shown during the project demonstration period. In order to assure that the information meets the user requirements, the actual information presented will be reviewed during the course of the demonstration in order to improve its quality and applicability. In addition to the project partners and the representatives of the Directorate of Fisheries, other possible expert users will be invited to use and evaluate the information content at the project web-site. In this respect the success evaluation criteria for the implementation of the DeciDe-HAB project will be pending on four main components:

5. Availability of EO data, i.e. acquisition and transmission of the data by the satellite system; real-time pre-processing and transmission of validated information products by the receiving station to the DeciDe-HAB project team.
6. Efficiency and quality of the system and information implemented within DeciDe-HAB project.
7. Appropriate definition and dissemination of the project concept, implementation and main outputs.
8. Feedback from HAB Management authorities to the DeciDe-HAB project team in terms of service evaluation and provision of *in situ* validation data.

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